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Procesos de transformación en el ámbito social bajo la ley marcial: retos y oportunidades

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Resumen. El propósito del estudio es analizar los cambios transformadores en la esfera social de Ucrania e identificar los desafíos y oportunidades actuales para el desarrollo de la esfera social. Se da el número aproximado de refugiados de Ucrania registrados en Europa y Asia a 12 de marzo de 2023, por país de destino. Se establece que la ley marcial ralentiza la economía, lo que provoca un aumento del desempleo y una disminución del nivel de vida. Se analiza la dinámica del PIB per cápita para 2013-2022 y la dinámica del desempleo en Ucrania en 2019-2023. Se determina que los acontecimientos militares en Ucrania crean una serie de problemas complejos, que van desde el impacto traumático en la población hasta desafíos significativos en el ámbito de la recuperación socioeconómica y la asistencia humanitaria. El autor analiza el daño a la esfera social a partir del 1 de enero de 2023 y presenta la estructura regional de las instituciones sociales afectadas. La atención se centra en el aumento significativo de los costos de la seguridad social. A pesar de las dificultades de la ley marcial en Ucrania, las principales oportunidades para el desarrollo de la esfera social incluyen la restauración de la infraestructura, la reforma del sistema educativo, el desarrollo de la rehabilitación médica y el apoyo psicológico. Ucrania puede convertirse en un centro de servicios psicológicos y apoyo humanitario,

así como desarrollar servicios sociales para grupos vulnerables. La participación de los ciudadanos y de los voluntarios contribuirá al desarrollo estable de la esfera social en el contexto de la recuperación de la posguerra.

Palabras clave: esfera social, desafíos, oportunidades de recuperación, ley marcial, grupos vulnerables.

Transformation processes in the social sphere under martial law: challenges and opportunities

Abstract. The purpose of the study is to analyze the transformational changes in the social sphere of Ukraine and to identify current challenges and opportunities for the development of the social sphere. The approximate number of refugees from Ukraine registered in Europe and Asia as of March 12, 2023, by country of destination is given. It is established that martial law slows down the economy, leading to an increase in unemployment and a decrease in living standards. The dynamics of GDP per capita for 2013-2022 and the dynamics of unemployment in Ukraine in 2019-2023 are analyzed. It is determined that the military events in Ukraine create a number of complex problems, ranging from traumatic impact on the population to significant challenges in the field of socio-economic recovery and humanitarian assistance. The author analyzes the damage to the social sphere as of January 1, 2023, and presents the regional structure of the affected social institutions. Attention is focused on the significant increase in social security costs. Despite the difficulties of martial law in Ukraine, the main opportunities for the development of the social sphere include the restoration of infrastructure, reform of the educational system, development of medical rehabilitation and psychological support. Ukraine can become a center for psychological services and humanitarian support, as well as develop social services for vulnerable groups. The involvement of citizens and volunteers will contribute to the stable development of the social sphere in the context of post-war recovery.

Keywords: social sphere, challenges, opportunities for recovery, martial law, vulnerable groups.

INTRODUCTION

Russia's invasion of Ukraine will have not only devastating economic consequences as it leads to the destruction of businesses, infrastructure and agriculture, closure of companies and loss of jobs, which is an inevitable result of martial law; but also a broad negative social effect - increased unemployment, growth in the number of displaced persons and people who have lost their homes, growth of the population temporarily under occupation, increased migration, impoverishment of the population, increased social insecurity of socially vulnerable groups of us. In addition, the hostilities increase the threat of socio-economic instability. A significant number of people are leaving the country due to the threat of insecurity and loss of employment opportunities, especially highly qualified professionals, who are a strategically important resource for economic development. The complete or partial destruction of schools, hospitals and other social institutions leads to a loss of access to education and healthcare services, which is particularly critical for children, the elderly

and people with disabilities. The loss of jobs and destroyed infrastructure has the greatest impact on vulnerable groups, including low-income people, leading to increased social inequality and reduced opportunities for improving living standards. Decreased business activity and job losses lead to a significant reduction in social contributions used to finance social programs and infrastructure. Stress, anxiety, and the constant threat of insecurity significantly worsen the mental health of the population, and traumatic events and the loss of loved ones lead to the spread of post-traumatic stress syndrome (PTSD) and other mental health problems. The growing need for humanitarian aid and medical services is becoming an important challenge for both the national and international community.

In addition, the issue of social rehabilitation of the military is becoming an urgent one, which is important in the context of the social consequences of war. Military personnel who have participated in combat operations may face post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD) and other mental health issues. It is also important to provide the military with access to high-quality medical care for the treatment of physical injuries and rehabilitation. An important task is to create conditions for the successful social integration of commissioned and discharged military personnel into civilian life through vocational rehabilitation, support in finding a job, and creating a favorable environment for their return to society. Providing psychosocial and social support for military families is also important, as families may face stress, changes in family environment and financial difficulties. Social rehabilitation should also include measures to protect the rights of veterans, including access to housing, medical care and other social services.

In sum, martial law has a significant negative impact on all spheres of life, from the economy and education to the mental health of the population. Overcoming these challenges will require a comprehensive and long-term approach on the part of the government and the public with the support of the international community, so there is a need to monitor the transformation processes in the social sphere to prepare adequate changes to social policy and to work proactively to assess the possible mitigation of the all-encompassing crisis in the social sphere and the growth of social tensions in society.

ANALYSIS OF THE LATEST RESEARCH AND PUBLICATIONS

The short-term social consequences of the war are terrible (Barceló, 2021): destruction of infrastructure (educational institutions, government agencies, medical facilities), weakening of economic and political institutions (reduced ability to finance the social sphere), human losses, an increase in the number of people in need of rehabilitation, social support, more people with disabilities, etc. Currently, there is no consensus in the scientific community on the long-term consequences of the war for society and development outcomes.

H. J. Colletta and M. L. Cullen, in their study of the World Bank, noted that the United Nations High Commissioner for Refugees (UNHCR), the United Nations Development Program (UNDP), and the World Bank have initiated programs that, according to the Brookings Institution, are aimed at reducing the gap between humanitarian aid and long-term development measures in countries after military conflicts. This transition from humanitarian assistance in times of conflict to development and peace efforts is becoming necessary due to socio-economic, political and psychological challenges in an uncertain security environment. Current responses to these challenges are insufficient due to the different approaches, institutional structures and funding systems of the

two types of actors - humanitarian and development. Humanitarian aid is usually characterized by fragility, and donors often show little interest in transition. Humanitarian operations are focused on rapid response and short-term planning, while development agents are often slow and inflexible. These two approaches tend to focus on their mandates rather than on the real needs of those affected by war. To address this gap, multilateral and bilateral institutions need to become more coherent in their strategies and operations. Joint missions of international organizations to West African countries such as Sierra Leone, Liberia and Guinea demonstrate the possibilities of governance in the realities of the sub-region. Focusing on cross-border issues, such as refugee and arms flows, natural resources, and security concerns, promotes synergies and improved coordination of policies and social programs at the local level (Colletta et al., 2000).

War inevitably and drastically changes social development and social cohesion, transforming development in the opposite direction: their legacy is permanent underdevelopment due to the weakening of local and national political institutions, the destruction of social protection, and the division of the population by removing the basis of norms, values and interpersonal and group trust that promotes interpersonal cooperation (Colletta et al., 2000; Kijewski et al., 2018). According to this view, armed conflicts have been found to negatively affect tangible factors such as investment, income, and consumption of individuals (Kijewski et al., 2018.), as well as less tangible elements such as psychological well-being and social trust (Deininger, 2003).

Among the positive effects of martial law on the social sphere are transformational institutional changes and changes in social priorities (Cramer, 2006; Morris, 2014; Verkhovod et al., 2023). Current research on the long-term impact of hostilities shows that those citizens who have suffered more from the war are more actively involved in broader collective activities after the conflict. This suggests that exposure to violence during war increases prosocial behavior. For example, J. Barzelo studied the impact of the intense conflict during the Vietnam War on Vietnamese society and conducted a representative survey in contemporary Vietnam, which includes the history of respondents' migration. The author concludes that conflict-affected individuals tend to be more involved in social organization and hold more distinct values, at least 26 years after the individual was involved in the war. Furthermore, the author found evidence that both individual persistence and community cohesion jointly explain the long-term increase in civic engagement. The results showed that individuals who lived in a province that was heavily affected by conflict during the war tended to be more involved in social organizations and have more distinct values, at least 26 years later (Barceló, 2021). The purpose of the study was to analyze the transformational changes in the social sphere of Ukraine and to identify current challenges and opportunities for the development of the social sphere.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

To achieve this goal, the appropriate methods were chosen. First of all, it is an analysis of literature sources to identify existing studies on the effects of military operations on the social sphere and the structure of society. This allowed us to form a basic understanding of the challenges faced by the state and society after the end of the war in the short and long term. The method of abstraction, as a universal approach, was also used to identify specific consequences that have a direct impact on the social sphere. The paper also uses the method of deduction, which allows us to study the challenges for the social sphere of Ukraine. This method facilitates the transition from generalizing general patterns to specific manifestations. In formulating the conclusions, the methods of systematization and generalization were used, which helped to summarize the results of the study.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Military conflicts have serious social consequences that can affect society for a long period after the end of the war. A year and a half after Russia's full-scale invasion, Ukraine has retaken 54% of the occupied territory, while Russia still occupies 18% of the country. During the 2023 offensive, Ukraine made minor territorial gains, but the front line remained stable for almost a year. Both sides have dug in, making breakthroughs increasingly difficult, and the number of military casualties has risen to about half a million on both sides. Meanwhile, Russia continues to bomb Ukrainian cities and blockade ports, and Ukraine has stepped up drone attacks on Russian ships and infrastructure (War in Ukraine. Center for Preventive Action, 2023). In Ukraine, large-scale military operations result in a large number of dead, wounded and maimed, which causes trauma and stress for families and society as a whole. Wounded soldiers need long-term medical and social support. There is also population migration, internal displacement, and an increase in the number of refugees and homeless people. Russia's constant missile and drone attacks lead to the destruction of cities, roads, infrastructure, schools and other facilities, which affects the development of society by disrupting traditional social structures. Martial law depresses the economy, leading to increased unemployment and lower living standards.

Since January 2022, Ukraine has received almost \$350 billion in aid, including \$77 billion from the United States. By the end of 2023, donor fatigue is evident. The fighting and airstrikes have caused a significant number of civilian casualties, with 5.1 million people internally displaced and 6.2 million migrating from Ukraine. About 17.6 million people are in need of humanitarian assistance (War in Ukraine. Center for Preventive Action, 2023).

The Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights (OHCHR) has confirmed a total of 9,614 civilian deaths during the Russian invasion of Ukraine as of September 2023. 17,535 injuries have also been reported. However, OHCHR clarified that the actual numbers may be higher. The highest number of deaths was recorded in March 2022 - more than 3.9 thousand. The Russian government authorities report data on the deaths of Ukrainian military, but at the moment they cannot be verified, so they should be treated with caution (Number of civilian casualties in Ukraine during Russia's invasion verified by OHCHR from February 24, 2022 to September 10, Statista, 2023). The Ukrainian authorities do not disclose casualties among their military.

Despite the fact that the flow of refugees from Ukraine is not as critical as it was at the beginning of the military invasion, the total number of people who migrated from Ukraine is reaching a significant level. As of December 31, 2022, almost 1.3 million refugees from Ukraine were registered in Russia due to the Russian invasion (Table 1).

In addition, approximately 970,000 were in Poland after leaving Ukraine as of September 3, 2023. In total, about six million Ukrainian refugees were registered in Europe and 6.2 million worldwide as of September 2023. Most of them left the country by crossing the border with Poland. As of September 2023, almost 1.09 million refugees from Ukraine were registered in Germany. The first increases in the number of Ukrainian refugees were registered in March and April 2022. At the end of January 2023, the German authorities officially counted more than one million refugees. The German authorities have offered the highest monthly cash assistance to Ukrainians fleeing the war compared to other European countries. Members of the European Union (EU) implemented the Temporary Protection Directive (TPD), which guaranteed refugees from Ukraine access to housing, social security, and medical care.

TABLE 1. Estimated number of refugees from Ukraine registered in Europe and Asia since February 2022 as of September 12, 2023 by the largest countries of destination.

Country	As of the date of	The number of refugees	Country	As of the date of	The number of refugees
russia	31.12.22	1275315	Estonia	01.09.23	50450
Germany	03.09.23	1086355	Lithuania	07.09.23	49970
Poland	03.09.23	968390	Turkey	24.08.23	43670
Czech Republic	9.10.23	368300	Sweden	07.09.23	41055
United Kingdom	01.08.23	210800	Denmark	27.08.23	39680
Spain	03.09.23	186125	Latvia	15.08.23	32470
Italy	11.08.23	167525	Belarus	01.08.23	32435
Moldova	9.10.23	116615	Georgia	25.07.23	27000
Slovakia	27.08.23	107415	Greece	30.06.23	25050
Netherlands	26.05.23	94415	Croatia	08.09.23	23070
Ireland	9.10.23	93810	Cyprus	27.08.23	18225
Romania	9.10.23	86810	North Macedonia	03.09.23	17315
Belgium	22.08.23	73095	Slovenia	04.09.23	10140
France	31.12.22	70570	Luxembourg	11.08.23	6065
Austria	9.11.23	68700	Serbia and Kosovo	31.08.23	5710
Switzerland	05.09.23	65800	Azerbaijan	28.08.23	4610
Bulgaria	9.12.23	65765	Albania	07.06.23	3800
Finland	9.10.23	61060	Iceland	21.08.23	3250
Portugal	04.06.23	56995	Malta	06.08.23	2235
Norway	30.08.23	56970	Armenia	17.07.23	605
Montenegro	04.09.23	56915	Liechtenstein	05.09.23	520
Hungary	03.09.23	53375	Bosnia and Herzegovina	27.08.23	190

Estimated number of refugees from Ukraine recorded in Europe and Asia since February 2022 as of September 12, 2023, by selected country. Statista, 2023.

Those fleeing the war were entitled to a residence permit in the EU, access to the labor market, and education for their children. The protection was granted for one year from the beginning of the war in February 2022, but it could be extended in the future depending on the situation in the country. Thus, Poland, Germany, and the Czech Republic had the highest number of people registered for temporary protection in the EU (Estimated number of refugees from Ukraine recorded in Europe and Asia since February 2022 as of September 12, 2023, by selected country. Statista, 2023).

As of May 23, 2023, there are approximately 5.1 million internally displaced persons in Ukraine, according to the international migration portal. More than half of all IDPs (60%) reported being displaced for one year or longer (Internally Displaced Persons (IDPs). Migration data portal, 2023).

The war affects people's incomes. Due to the decline in business activity, the level of material security is deteriorating, as evidenced by the decline in GDP per capita (Figura 1). This indicator indicates the general state of well-being of the population.

Figura 1. Dynamics of GDP per capita in 2013-2022 (GDP in Ukraine falls 29.1. Country Economy, 2023).

As we can see, both the annexation of Crimea and the occupation of parts of Donetsk and Luhansk regions and the current Russian invasion have had a significant negative impact on the level of GDP per capita. Ukraine's GDP fell by -29.1% in 2022 compared to the previous year. In 2022, the GDP amounted to \$160,503 million, and Ukraine ranks 59th in the GDP ranking of 196 countries. The absolute value of GDP in Ukraine fell by \$39,652 million compared to 2021. In 2022, Ukraine's GDP per capita amounted to \$3,915, which is \$967 less than in 2021, when it was \$4,882 (GDP in Ukraine falls 29.1. Country Economy, 2023). The decline in GDP per capita indicates a complex negative impact of the war on the economic situation of the state, primarily a decline in business activity, a decline in industrial production, low investment activity, and general instability. This negative trend leads to limited access to education, healthcare and other social services. In addition, the decline in this indicator leads to a reduction in consumer activity, as people may be limited in their purchasing power. In general, a decline in GDP per capita indicates problems in the economy and a decline in the quality of life of citizens. A general decline in the country's economic potential leads to an increase in unemployment.

According to the NBU's updated estimate, the unemployment rate in Ukraine was 21.1% in 2022. The government plans to reduce the unemployment rate in Ukraine to 19% in 2023 (Prasad, 2023). According to the IMF, the unemployment rate in Ukraine in 2022 was 24.5%, with a projected decline to 19.4% by the end of 2023 (Figura 2).

In general, the military conflict is a serious challenge for the economy and employment, and its impact on unemployment leads to an increase in the level of vulnerable groups.

Figura 2. Unemployment dynamics in Ukraine in 2019-2023 according to (Unemployment rate. IMF, 2023).

In addition, social institutions are being devastated. According to the KSE (Unemployment rate. IMF, 2023), as of January 2023, at least 4497 social, educational, and healthcare institutions suffered direct damage as a result of Russia’s full-scale invasion, which began on February 24, 2022. According to KSE Institute project experts, the total amount of direct losses for social, educational, and healthcare institutions is estimated at \$10.7 billion (Table 2).

Of this amount, \$0.2 billion is damage to the social sector, \$8.8 billion is damage to educational institutions, and \$1.8 billion is damage to healthcare institutions. The total indirect losses amounted to \$11.1 billion, and the amount needed to repair them is at least \$19.7 billion. The total number of damaged or destroyed educational facilities is over 3,127, including 1,489 schools, 885 kindergartens and 517 university buildings. Healthcare facilities were damaged or destroyed almost three times less - 1245 facilities. Among the medical facilities, outpatient clinics suffered the most - 430 facilities and 362 hospitals. Also, 154 social security institutions were damaged or destroyed. The most affected were sanatoriums - 46 institutions, social welfare centers - 43, and boarding schools - 31. Losses in the social sphere, medicine and education as a result of Russian aggression are estimated at \$10.8 billion. KSE, 2023). The regions where social protection institutions suffered the most are shown in Figura 3.

The social sphere suffered the most destruction in Donetsk region (21%), Odesa region (20%), and the city of Kyiv (18%).

Figura 4 shows the regional structure of the affected educational and healthcare institutions. The greatest damage was done to these institutions in Donetsk, Kharkiv and Luhansk regions due to the highest intensity of hostilities in these regions.

Figura 3. Regional structure of affected social institutions

TABLE 2. KSE Institute's estimate of losses to the social sphere, social, education, and healthcare institutions as of January 1, 2023.

Sphere	Name of the institutions	Amount of losses, mln USD
Social sphere	Sanatoriums	79,5
	Boarding schools	55,1
	Social centers	25
	Children's camps	15,6
	Institutions for the elderly	9,4
	Children's homes	3,3
	Institutions for the homeless	0,1
	Total	188
Healthcare	Hospitals	1430
	Other institutions	169,6
	Outpatient facilities	96,9
	Polyclinics	75,5
	Blood centers	17,6
	Total	1789,6
Educational sphere	Higher education institutions	3795,5
	Secondary education institutions	3298,2
	Institutions of preschool education	1043,8
	Vocational education institutions	413,7
	Out-of-school education institutions	86,4
	Vocational education institutions	39,2
	Total	8676,8
Other institutions		108,2
	Together	10762,6

Unemployment rate. IMF; 2023.

Figura 4. Regional structure of affected educational and healthcare institutions

In addition to the direct damage to the destroyed social infrastructure, social security costs have increased significantly, driven by a significant increase in unemployment and the number of unemployed internally displaced persons, which leads to social tensions. As of mid-2022, additional state budget expenditures to cover the need for social benefits, based on the number of internally displaced persons and other categories of citizens (excluding unemployment costs) who additionally need social support, are estimated at USD 6.4 billion. In its June report, the World Bank estimated the needs for reconstruction of the social, healthcare and education sectors at \$44.9 billion. It is expected that the estimate of these reconstruction needs is not final, as the situation in the social sphere will directly depend on further escalation of hostilities and other factors related to the hostilities - an increase in the number of vulnerable groups due to the growing number of war veterans, internally displaced persons, persons who have lost their breadwinners, become disabled, etc. (Losses in the social sphere, medicine and education as a result of Russian aggression are estimated at \$10.8 billion. KSE, 2023).

Currently, the social sphere of Ukraine is undergoing significant transformational changes. The martial law in relation to the social sphere in Ukraine leads to deep and complex transformations of a comprehensive nature and creates a number of challenges:

- direct damage from hostilities causes the destruction of social infrastructure, such as schools, hospitals, and other institutions;
- destruction of social institutions leads to limited access to education, healthcare and other social services for the population;
- damage to the educational sector necessitates large-scale reconstruction of schools, higher education institutions and kindergartens;
- loss of access to education for thousands of children and youth may have far-reaching consequences for the further development of society;
- the destruction of health care facilities leads to insufficient medical care and treatment for the victims;
- there is an increase in the need for psychological and psychiatric care due to the stressful conditions of a prolonged war;
- unemployment is increasing due to the destruction of economic infrastructure and businesses and the need to support them;
- changes in the demographic situation due to human casualties, internal displacement of the population and migration of women and children abroad, deportation of children from the occupied regions to the Russian Federation;
- increased need for social support for internally displaced persons, families who have lost a breadwinner, war veterans and other vulnerable groups;
- increased social expenditures and reconstruction efforts put great financial pressure on the state budget in the context of its total deficit and subsidization by international organizations;
- increased number of vulnerable groups, such as children, the elderly and the disabled;
- lack of or limited access to social services due to the destruction and suspension of social institutions, and the significant occupation of the territory;
- risk of epidemics due to limited access to sanitation and medical resources.

All of these challenges put enormous pressure on the social sector and require comprehensive and long-term measures to restore and support the population in the context of armed conflict.

In general, martial law significantly worsens the state of the social sphere, causing the need for a wide range of measures to restore and ensure the social well-being of the population. Subsequently, the social policy response includes not only the restoration of physical structures, but also the development of social programs and psychological support aimed at restoring a favorable environment for people in difficult martial law conditions.

Despite the difficulties and challenges associated with martial law, there are certain opportunities for the development of Ukraine's social sector both during and after the end of the war. First and foremost, it is the restoration of infrastructure through the implementation of targeted programs and funding to rebuild destroyed facilities such as schools, hospitals and social centers and the development and implementation of initiatives to create new and modernize existing social institutions. In the area of education, developing initiatives to ensure access to education for all segments of the population, including internally displaced persons and children affected by the war, with the assistance of international organizations, will strengthen and reform the education system, with a focus on supporting vocational training and retraining programs for people who have lost their jobs due to the war. There are great opportunities for Ukraine in terms of medical rehabilitation and psychological support. Ukraine can become a global center for launching psychological services, developing and testing effective support systems for those who have faced stress and trauma as a result of military events. Ukraine will need to develop social services for vulnerable groups to increase the availability of social services for children, the elderly, the disabled, and others in need, and can receive humanitarian support for these programs from international organizations or invite them to conduct special missions in Ukraine after the war ends. In addition, the end of the war will create a favorable environment for the development of innovations in the social sphere to attract financial support for social startups and projects aimed at improving living conditions after the war.

Active involvement of citizens and volunteers in social development projects at the current stage will further strengthen the cohesion of Ukrainian society and aim it at solving pressing social problems by creating platforms and initiatives that promote community interaction and support. These opportunities involve cooperation between the government, civil society, international organizations and volunteer groups to achieve successful and sustainable results in the development of the social sphere in the context of post-war recovery.

CONCLUSIONS

Ukraine is facing significant social challenges as a result of the Russian aggression - a large number of dead, wounded and internally displaced persons, destroyed infrastructure, loss of housing and large-scale migration flows, destruction of cities, schools and social institutions - which leads to severe trauma and stress for the population. The significant number of refugees from Ukraine, which reaches millions, poses extraordinary challenges for host countries. The financial assistance received from international donors helps to save lives and provide the necessary assistance, but there is a risk of donor fatigue, which can lead to difficulties in the future. One of the key problems is the high unemployment rate caused by economic instability and the suspension of business operations due to the hostilities. Martial law slows down the economy, leading to higher unemployment and lower living standards. In general, the military events in Ukraine are causing a number of complex

problems, ranging from traumatic impact on the population to significant challenges in the area of socio-economic recovery and humanitarian assistance. The decline in economic potential as a result of the war leads to limited access to education, healthcare and other social services. It also leads to a reduction in consumer activity, which is reflected in a deterioration in the quality of life. In addition to direct losses, the war has also led to an increase in social welfare spending due to rising unemployment and other social challenges. This puts a lot of pressure on the state budget and society, requiring rapid and effective recovery and social support strategies for the affected industries and population, and generates the need for a wide range of measures to restore and support the population, including infrastructure reconstruction, social programs, psychological assistance, and effective social policies.

Despite the difficulties of martial law in Ukraine, there are opportunities for the development of the social sector both during and after the end of the war. Key opportunities include rebuilding infrastructure, reforming the education system, and developing medical rehabilitation and psychological support. Ukraine could become a center for psychological services and humanitarian support, as well as the development of social services for vulnerable groups. The development of social innovations and the involvement of citizens and volunteers will contribute to the sustainable development of the social sphere in the post-war recovery.

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